
CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS DURABLE GOODS – A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO MAYILADUTHURAI TOWN

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Introduction:

Consumer behaviour is the study of how individual customers, groups or organizations select, buy, use, and dispose ideas, goods, and services to satisfy their needs and wants. It refers to the actions of the consumers in the marketplace and the underlying motives for those actions. Marketers expect that by understanding what causes the consumers to buy particular goods and services, they will be able to determine which products are needed in the marketplace, which are obsolete, and how best to present the goods to the consumers.

Definition:

According to Engel, Blackwell, and Mansard, 'consumer behaviour is the actions and decision processes of people who purchase goods and services for personal consumption'.

According to Loudon and Bitta, 'consumer behaviour is the decision process and physical activity, which individuals engage in when evaluating, acquiring, using or disposing of goods and services'.

Statement of the Problem

Consumer is nerve centre of the trendy promoting, understanding his behavior is kind of essential for economical and effective promoting management. Customers could state their desires, desires however act otherwise. They'll not be in-tuned with their deeper motivations. India's client market is riding the crest of the country's economic boom. Driven by a young population with access to disposable incomes and simple finance choices, the buyers market has been throwing up staggering figures. Promoting drawback enhancing from the buyers' behavior contains a larger degree of similarity behavioral issues about the consumer durables. Hence, this study has been chosen to spot and ascertain the extent of issues of client behavior have a sway on the promoting of durable goods within the quick growing Mayiladuthurai. The buyer behavior in about durable goods is powerfully full of some demographic factors; this analysis has been chosen for an intensive empirical survey of the assorted factors influencing the buyer's behavior on durable goods in Mayiladuthurai Town for the system behavior to complete.

Objective of the study

1. To study the demographic profile of the consumers of durable goods.
2. To identify and analyse the demographic factors determining the consumer's buying preference of Durable goods.
3. To identify the source of awareness about durable goods.
4. To study the factors which are influencing brand preference for different brands of durable goods.

Methodology

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected from the consumers of durable goods through a well-designed questionnaire. The required secondary data were also collected from journal and magazines which are highly relevant to the topic of the study.

Sampling

The study is mainly based on primary data sample size selected for the study is 75 respondents of the

selected consumer durable goods in Mayiladuthurai town. The samples are selected by adopting convenient sampling technique.

Limitation of the study

The study was subject to the following limitation:

1. The study is confirmed only to Mayiladuthurai Town.
2. Due to lack of time, the sample size is restricted only with 75.
3. The study is restricted only with home appliances only.

Gender wise classification of the Respondents

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Male	42	56%
2	Female	33	44%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

From the table shows that 56% of the respondents are belongs to the male category and 44% of the respondents are female category. It is understood from the above analysis that most of the respondents taken in to study are male.

Age wise classification of the Respondents

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Upto 25 years	14	19%
2	26 to 35 years	34	45%
3	36 to 45 years	18	24%
4	Above 45 years	9	12%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

From the table depicts that out of 75 customers, 45% belonged to age category of 26 to 35 years, 24% belonged to the age category of 26 to 45 years, 19% of customer belonged to the age category of upto 25 years and the rest of 12% pertaining to the age category of above 45 years.

This analysis clearly reveals the most of the sample respondents i.e., 45% are representing the age category of 26 to 35 years.

Education wise classification of the Respondents

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Upto school level	9	12%
2	Graduate	31	41%
3	Post graduate	20	27%
4	Professionals	11	15%
5	Others	4	5%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

From the table, it can be inferred that 41% of the respondents are graduate, 27% of the respondents are completed their post graduate degree, 15% of the respondents are professional people, 12% of the respondents are come under the category of upto school level education and the remaining 5% representing the other, which includes diploma certificate programming, etc.,

This analysis clearly indicates that all the respondents considered for the study are literate.

Marital status of the Respondents

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Married	58	77%
2	Unmarried	17	23%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

From the table noticed that 77% of the respondents are got married and the remaining 23% are unmarried. This reveals that a vast majority of the respondents are taken for the study is married.

Occupation wise classification of the Respondents

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Employees	32	43%
2	Profession	8	11%
3	Business	20	27%
4	Agriculturist	5	6%
5	Others	10	13%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

From the table, we came to know that 43% of the respondents were salaried employees, 27% were doing their own business, 11% of respondents were professionals, 6% of respondents were agriculturalist and 13% of respondents were comes under other category, which includes students, house wife, etc., It clears that the maximum number of respondents taken under study were employees.

Income wise classification of the Respondents

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Upto Rs.10,000	18	24%
2	Rs.10,001 to Rs.20,000	30	40%
3	Rs.20,001 to Rs.30,000	15	20%
4	More than Rs.30,000	12	16%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

The table portrays that out of 75 respondents, 30 belonged to the category of Rs.10,000 to Rs.20,000, 18 respondents belonged to the category of upto Rs.5000, 15 respondent belonged to the category of Rs.20,001 to Rs.30,000 and 12 customer belonged to the category of more than Rs.30,000. This analysis reveals that most of the respondent's monthly income was between Rs.10,001 to Rs.20,000.

Purchase decision maker

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Husband	21	28%
2	Wife	15	20%
3	Elder members	9	12%
4	Collectively	30	40%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

Table reveals that in 30 families the purchase decision was taken collectively by all members of the family, in 21 families husband took a decision to purchase a particular brand, on 15 families' wife took a purchase decision and only in 9 families the purchase decision was taken by elder members. This analysis clearly exhibits that majority of the sample respondents (i.e., 40%) said that the purchase decision was taken collectively by all members of the family.

Sources of Information

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Advertisement	25	33%
2	Friends & Relatives	48	64%
3	Dealers / Retailers	14	19%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

From the above table, illustrate the source of information from where they got information about the brand of durable goods they have purchased. 48% of the respondents said they got information from the friends and relatives, 33% got information through advertisement and rest 19% got information forever dealers/relatives. This analysis clearly envisage that most of the respondents taken into study got information about the brand of durable goods they have purchased through friends & relatives.

Factors influencing the purchase decision of Durable goods

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Price	29	39%
2	Technology	10	13%
3	After sale service	14	19%
4	Warranty	22	29%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

From the table, reveals that 39% of the respondents opined that price is the prime factor for making purchase decision, 19% of the consumer viewed that warranty is the motivating factor for taking purchase decision, 19% of the consumer felt that after sale service is the influencing factor for purchase decision, only 13% of the respondents stated that technology adopted is the inducing factor for making purchasing decision regarding durable goods.

Satisfaction with Durable Products

Sl.No	Factors	Respondents	
		in No.	in %
1	Satisfied	43	57%
2	Neutral	24	32%
3	Not satisfied	8	11%
Total		75	100%

Source: Primary data

From the table, clearly depicts that 57% of the respondents are satisfied with the durable products which are purchased by them, 32% of the consumer considered for the study viewed that they are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their product. The remaining 11% of the respondents opined that they are dissatisfied with the product.

Findings

The following are the various findings arrived in the present study.

1. Majority of the respondents considered for the study are belongs to male category (56%)
2. Most of the sample respondents i.e., 45% are representing the age category of 26 to 35 years.
3. All the respondents taken into study are literate. Only a very little % i.e., 12% are completed their school level education.
4. Majority of the respondents (77%) are married.
5. The maximum number of consumers taken under study were salaried employees.
6. Most of the respondents monthly income was between Rs.10,001 to Rs.20,000.
7. Majority of the sample respondents (i.e., 40%) said that the purchase decision was taken collectively by all members of the family.
8. 57% of the sample respondents are satisfied with the durable products which are purchased by them.

Suggestions:

- i) The marketer must conduct consumer based research with a view to access the needs and wants of the customers.
- ii) The marketer must constantly monitor the consumer purchase behavior through local retailers and seek their assistance in curbing fake brands.
- iii) The markets / dealers must address the various problems faced by the customers like poor service quality, lack of replacement facility, high prices etc., This will help to improve the customer satisfaction and pave the way for customer loyalty.

Conclusion

Now-a-days, the market for consumer durables is becoming more competitive. Hence, the manufacturers of durable goods should understand consumer interest much to find higher sale of their products. From this study, it can be concluded that the demographic variables do have an impact on the buying pattern of the consumer with reference durable goods. Hence, suggestion provided from this study will assist the producers of durable goods to earn more profit and increasing their market share.

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